

Evaluating the Socio-economic effects of reducing antimicrobial use in the pig industry: lessons learned from the French Ecoantibio 1 programme

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1. Summary

Recent public policies aimed at reducing the use of antimicrobials in animal production have been successful when measured by the quantity of antimicrobial use, as usage has decreased in all production sectors. However, the key factors for the success of these policies and their socio-economic effects are poorly known. A qualitative survey conducted among the actors of the pig production unveils them.

20 **2. Abstract**

21 The fight against antimicrobial resistance (AMR) represents one of the major public health
22 challenges of the 21st century. As an important user of antimicrobials, animal agriculture
23 contributes to the risk of resistance in public health. In France, a five-year voluntary plan, the
24 Ecoantibio 1 programme, was implemented in 2012, to reduce antimicrobial use in the livestock
25 sector. Ecoantibio 1 programme consists of a research, executive education and outreach
26 programme coordinated by the Ministry of Agriculture, and involving many livestock
27 stakeholders. The aim of this study is to carry out a retrospective evaluation of the programme
28 in the pig sector using a qualitative approach.

29 Results show that the Ecoantibio 1 programme had a moderate impact on farming practices, the
30 structural modifications and the economics of the value chain. The programme fostered an
31 ongoing dynamic initiated by other public policies and private initiatives on antimicrobial use,
32 such as the prohibition of the last generation cephalosporins. Similarly, most of the medical
33 alternatives to antimicrobials such as vaccination or biosecurity programmes already existed
34 and were being used before Ecoantibio. Nevertheless, the plan supported their adoption and use
35 in the field and strengthened the dynamics already in progress. The evaluation also indicates
36 that stakeholder relations in the pork sector have been little impacted by the programme or have
37 even been strengthened. Ultimately, and even though having no major impact on pig growth
38 rates or on the incomes of the different stakeholders, the Ecoantibio 1 programme amplified an
39 ongoing dynamic, speeded the adoption of technical changes and reinforced the prudent use of
40 antimicrobials by stakeholder. The study shows how an entire value chain can collectively
41 adjust its perspectives regarding a topic initially considered as very hard to change.

43 **3. Introduction**

44 Like other chemical inputs, antimicrobials, thanks to their capability to control infectious
45 diseases, were part of the green revolution, which allowed for a drastic increase in farm
46 productivity and made food of animal origin more affordable {Bentley, 2003 #12662;Pingali,
47 2012 #12704;Steinfeld, 2010 #12703}. In swine production, antimicrobials are used in three
48 circumstances: (i) in individual medicine to treat a sick animal, (ii) in collective medicine (to
49 treat batches of animals) when a percentage of animals in the batch is sick (metaphylaxis), (iii)
50 in prevention before the appearance of the disease, on all the animals of a batch on which the
51 probability of disease appearance is considered high (prophylaxis). By treating or seeking to
52 prevent the occurrence of certain diseases, antimicrobial use (AMU) respond to several
53 challenges: (i) animal welfare, in the context of optimizing the quality of care, (ii) economics,
54 since diseases impact food products value chain through change in quantity and quality, and (iii)
55 public health, in the fight against contagious infectious diseases and particularly zoonoses
56 (animal diseases that can be transmitted to humans){Lhermie, 2017 #3885}. Although
57 relatively effective and inexpensive products, their use is not risk-free. In the short term, the
58 direct risks of using antimicrobials in livestock production for animals and/or consumers,
59 associated with antimicrobial toxicity, overdosage and/or presence of antimicrobial residues,
60 are very low. In France, as in many countries, their market is regulated by the Public Health
61 Code. This regulation sets maximum residue limits in food products of animal origin for all
62 drugs used in livestock production, in order to guarantee food safety {LegiFrance, 2021a
63 #12677;LegiFrance, 2021b #12678}. For ensuring the above, a withdrawal period – time
64 between the last administration of a veterinary medicine and the slaughter of the animal – is
65 established according to the competent authorities {European Parliament and the Council of the
66 European Union, 2019 #12728}. In addition, adverse effects reported by owners of animals
67 who have been treated by antimicrobials are very rare {ANSES, 2021 #12661}. With the

68 growing consciousness of the mid and long-term impact of antimicrobial misuse, present
69 concerns are focused on the increased indirect risk of the selection of antimicrobial-resistant
70 pathogens, leading to a progressive decrease in the effectiveness of antimicrobials in treating
71 bacterial diseases.

72 Resistant bacteria can be transmitted to humans, either by direct animal-human contact, or via
73 the environment, or via the food chain {Williams-Nguyen, 2016 #12692}. Public health costs
74 due to antimicrobial resistance (AMR) take different forms, monetary and non-monetary. This
75 resistance leads to increased lengths of hospital stay, greater morbidity and mortality, and
76 increased costs of care. In 2019, the global number of deaths associated with antimicrobial-
77 resistant bacteria was estimated at 4.95 million (3.62–6.57), which included 1.27 million (95%
78 Uncertainty Interval 0.911–1.71) deaths attributable to antimicrobial-resistant bacteria
79 {Murray, 2022 #12705}. According to the World Bank, by 2050, the yearly increase in
80 healthcare cost in the public sector due to antimicrobial resistance can range from US\$300
81 billion to more than US\$1 trillion {Ahmad, 2019 #12706}. In France, recent studies estimate
82 that infections with resistant bacteria represent around 140,000 cases, 5,500 deaths and a total
83 cost of 290€ million per year {Touat, 2019 #12688}. Globalisation and international trade also
84 play a role in this emerging health concern, with food supply chains and transport routes
85 offering the means to move the risk of disease due to resistant bacteria between regions and
86 countries. This is particularly relevant considering the uneven national legislations regulating
87 the use of antimicrobials in livestock production {Avraam, 2021 #12707}.

88 Although the contribution of the use of antimicrobials in agriculture to antimicrobial resistance
89 in human health is ultimately poorly quantified {Landers, 2012 #12711;Singer, 2014
90 #12710;Chang, 2015 #12709}, the public health risk justifies that all agricultural sectors make
91 an effort to reduce its use. As such, public policies aimed at reducing the use of antimicrobials
92 in animal production have been put in place to mitigate this public health risk in many countries.

93 For example, the European Parliament banned the use of antimicrobials as growth promoters in
94 animal feed in 2000 {European Union, 2003 #12670}. Several countries have now set up plans
95 to control antimicrobial resistance, which is also the subject of actions coordinated worldwide
96 by the World Health Organization, the World Organisation for Animal Health, and the
97 Organization for Food and Agriculture {OIE, 2016 #12681;World Health, 2016 #12690;FAO,
98 2016 #12693}.

99 In France, several regulatory and voluntary measures have been implemented. A moratorium
100 to reduce the use of third and fourth generation cephalosporins, led by the French pig farmers
101 and veterinarians, came into light in 2011 within the pig value chain, which agreed on using these
102 antimicrobials solely at last resort {Hémonic, 2018 #12694}. In 2012, the French government
103 launched the five-year program Ecoantibio 1 programme that aimed at reducing the
104 consumption of antimicrobials in livestock sectors by 25% {ANSES, 2011 #12660}. This plan
105 is a voluntary programme set up on the initiative of the Ministry of Agriculture in 2012
106 {Ministère de l’Agriculture de la Pêche et de la Ruralité, 2011 #12682}. Many actors from the
107 pharmaceutical system and the food system have been involved in this. Some recommendations
108 made by the programme were juridically anchored in the so-called Future Law for Agriculture,
109 Food and Forestry, which was enforced in January 2015 {Ministère de l’Agriculture de la
110 Pêche et de la Ruralité, 2014 #12683}. Although not specifically targeting AMU, it has
111 provided the legal basis for regulating the use of critically important antimicrobials. Noteworthy
112 measures were the mandatory use of sensitivity tests before prescribing antimicrobials, their
113 prescription only after clinical examination of the animals, and the ban of a certain type of
114 discounts by resellers. The Ecoantibio 1 plan was a great success, with a decrease in AMU by
115 35 % in 5 years. The swine sector was a heavy AMU user before the Ecoantibio 1 plan, and
116 remains high at the end of the plan in spite of an important decrease. In 2018, 35% of the
117 tonnage of antimicrobials sold by veterinary pharmaceutical laboratories were intended for pigs

118 (around 167 tonnes), 29% for cattle and 18% for poultry {ANSES, 2019 #12658}. Overall,
119 AMU in the pig sector fell by 47% over the period of 2010-2016, and the use of medicated
120 premix plummeted (-74% over 2011-2018).

121 This rapid and massive reduction in use raises questions about its effects for the various
122 stakeholders. If all things were kept equal, reducing or removing the use of antimicrobials in
123 pig production could hamper farmers' ability to manage disease pressure, with an increase in
124 morbidity and mortality affecting the productivity of the animals. Studies in the US have
125 estimated the ban in the use of antimicrobials for growth promotion (AGP) in the swine sector
126 to increase production costs and decrease net profits. In Denmark, a study led by a WHO panel
127 has indicated similar findings resulting from the same policy, with net production costs per pig
128 produced increasing 1.04€ {Laxminarayan, 2015 #12712}. On the other hand, improved
129 biosecurity and adequate and effective vaccination plans could replace AMU in pig production
130 in a cost-effective manner, even with added labour costs {Dewulf, 2022 #12713}. Reducing
131 AMU in pig production could also mean less income from their sales to veterinarians. If this is
132 their main revenue stream, the impact would be substantial. Contrarily, moving away from
133 antibiotic sales to increased farm advisory could mitigate the impact to the veterinary business.
134 The aim of this study is to carry out a retrospective assessment of the Ecoantibio 1 programme
135 over its implementation period in the pig sector through a qualitative research approach, and
136 evaluate its impact in stakeholders across the value chain. In this article, we present and discuss
137 the results of semi-structured interviews, intended to collect information on 6 evaluative
138 questions: (1) the effects of the program on the different actors (changes in practices, interplay
139 between actors, structural effects); (2) effects on farm incomes; (3) effects on other supply
140 chains; (4) acceptability and most influential measures; (5) effects on pig health; (6) and the
141 effects of alternatives to antimicrobials.

142 4. Materials and Methods

143 4.1. Data collection

144 Semi-structured interviews were conducted, in order to collect information (i) that could
145 provide explanations or factual elements on the role of the Ecoantibio 1 plan in reducing AMU
146 in the sector swine and (ii) reveal indirect effects of the plan. Six blocks of questions were
147 developed for the semi-structured interviews, with priority questions (presented below) and
148 follow-up questions (see supplementary material).

149

150 Q.1: what were the effects of the Ecoantibio 1 programme on the various players in the
151 sector? Do some benefit more than others, if so which ones, why and how? For example,
152 is this the case for veterinarians (in terms of advice, consultation and sales) and sanitary
153 defense groups?

154 Q.2: How does the Ecoantibio 1 programme act on the different types of costs and
155 benefits of a pig farm?

156 Q.3: Has the application of the Ecoantibio 1 programme to the pig sector had positive
157 or negative repercussions on the cattle and poultry sectors (for example in terms of
158 purchasing substitutions)?

159 Q.4: Which measures of the Ecoantibio 1 programme have had the most positive or
160 negative influences, by acting in what ways and on what?

161 Q.5: What were the consequences of the Ecoantibio 1 programme on the health and
162 growth of pigs?

163 Q.6: Have alternative measures been taken to reduce AMU, for example the use of
164 probiotics or other growth factors, biocontrol, health measures, etc.?

165

166 The data collection was carried out between December 2020 and March 2021, on a convenient
167 sample of thirty-three participants, holding various positions in the sector. The interviews lasted
168 between 24 and 90 minutes, for a total of 23 hours 10 minutes, and took place remotely (by
169 videoconference or telephone). The interviews were recorded through Zoom and transcribed.
170 Selected participants were contacted by phone or email to provide information on the rationale
171 of the study. At the beginning of the interview, participants were informed that the conversation
172 would remain anonymous, and that any material leading to a potential identification of the
173 individual would be removed from the analysis.

174 **4.2. Data treatment**

175 Verbatim interviews were manually transcribed. Responses were then analyzed for themes and
176 topic areas that are echoed by many respondents, as well as areas that they highlight as critical
177 or most important. Text fragments were identified in relation with the 6 overarching questions.
178 Triangulation principle was applied to ensure construction of coherent themes. A member
179 checking was done by presenting the results during one stakeholder meeting, gathered by the
180 French Ministry of Agriculture, as stipulated in the grant agreement funding the study.

181 **5. Results & Discussion**

182 **5.1. Changes in farmer practices**

183 The Ecoantibio 1 plan has encouraged farmers to change their view of their farming practices,
184 in favour of a more rational use of antimicrobials. Indeed, the psychological trigger of the actors
185 in the field is a key lever for a sustainable change in farming practices.

186 The vaccination strategy is the main alternative used to limit the use of antimicrobials, but it
187 started long before the start of the plan. During the Ecoantibio 1 plan, stakeholders reported that

188 vaccination has mainly been developed for the respiratory axis (circovirus, PRRS), the digestive
189 axis (colibacilli) and piglet edema, helping to improve health advice, among other things.
190 Vaccines began replacing antimicrobials by playing a “patch” role, without considering all the
191 risk factors. Moreover, it is often in the face of poor animal husbandry practices that vaccination
192 is adopted. Even if the Ecoantibio 1 plan has been able to play an accelerating role in the spread
193 of vaccination, it has settled into a dynamic already at work, of rising prices of medicated feed,
194 reducing specialties available, and raising awareness among farmers.

195 Another practice for optimising the use of antimicrobials was highlighted during our
196 investigation: that of the use of dosing pumps. A dosing pump is a farming tool that allows
197 direct targeting of animals and application of the treatment dose for a health problem, by
198 strongly limiting systematic treatment through feed. The dosing pumps were generally already
199 installed before the implementation of the plan. According to a survey participant, about 3% of
200 farmers would have equipped themselves during the period. However, the Ecoantibio 1 plan
201 was able to play an accelerating role in their installation in post-weaning, and therefore in the
202 prescription of the associated oral powders. The spread of pumps can also occur after
203 discontinuation of the use of antimicrobials in food supplementation or following the
204 appearance of new solutions and new products using pumps. Dosing pumps mainly play a role
205 of “transitional safety measure” towards the discontinuation of medicated feed.

206 Developed by feed manufacturers, safe feeds have the role of strengthening the immune system
207 of piglets during their first age. However, raw materials are generally replaced by cheap
208 materials; the adaptation of piglets to these changes is often difficult, leading to digestive drifts.
209 Some cooperatives have marketed secure feed with a low protein content, causing slower
210 growth in piglets. This type of problem may have caused dissatisfaction among farmers or even
211 a return to antimicrobials, but it is not a significant phenomenon over the period of the plan.
212 These feed solutions were largely developed counter-current to the plan; they took place in a

213 context of reduced use of antimicrobials, promoted by an improvement in awareness and
214 demand from groups in terms of specifications. Although farmers may perceive secure feed as
215 less effective than antimicrobials, the increasingly limited use of antimicrobials has fostered the
216 search for alternatives. Safe feeds have been more widely adopted in the phases of
217 discontinuation of antimicrobial use, such as when stopping early colistin supplementation.
218 During the Ecoantibio 1 plan, a significant drop in the quantity and number of medicated feed
219 specialties was observed, which may be correlated with the implementation of the plan.
220 However, the reduction in the use of medicated feed may have encountered certain difficulties,
221 in particular because this type of supplementation was integrated into farming practices.
222 The Ecoantibio 1 plan has helped to revise these farming practices and put zootechnicians back
223 at the center of discussions on risk management. Even if part of an ongoing dynamic,
224 zootechnicians are increasingly committed to the reduction on the use of antimicrobials,
225 through the adoption of good farming practices and prophylactic measures. Given the
226 multifactorial nature of health problems, it is possible to address them upstream through the
227 management of zootechnical factors. However, economic factors must also be taken into
228 account; for example, reducing the density of animals in a building improves welfare and can
229 limit the spread of disease, but handling costs are then higher {Schodl, 2021 #12714;Hayek,
230 2022 #12715;Jones, 2013 #12716}. Among the zootechnical measures, a greater weight of
231 piglets at weaning makes it possible to limit digestive problems, but too much time spent in the
232 weaning room can also have significant impacts on technical and economic performance.
233 Biosafety has not been placed at the heart of the plan, but it is an essential tool for achieving a
234 sustainable reduction in the use of antimicrobials. Cleaning and disinfection, ventilation and
235 loading must be put at the center of the sanitary conduct, among others. However, too much
236 investment in air filtration and improving pig comfort may weaken their immune system.

237 Herbal medicine is probably developed; but these products do not have any Marketing
238 Authorization (AMM), which makes it difficult to quantify the flows intended for them and
239 there is little information on this subject. Even if the demand increases among farmers, the lack
240 of control remains in terms of safety and effectiveness. Herbal medicine is generally used as an
241 adjunct to vaccination, to regulate the intestinal flora for example. It is then not a question of a
242 pure substitution, but of a complement.

243

244 **5.2. Structural transformations induced by the plan**

245 The decline in the use of antimicrobials is generally considered to be the result of a collective
246 approach between food manufacturers, farmers and veterinarians. Thanks to the financing of
247 projects, the plan has promoted better veterinary supervision in the event of the occurrence of a
248 health crisis.

249 Some stakeholders mention that the issue of the reduction in the use of antimicrobials is not the
250 reduction in quantities but, above all, veterinary practice, as well as the improvement of animal
251 welfare and health. The logic of administering medicinal inputs by default has gradually shifted
252 towards responsible veterinary practice. Generally, the farmer places great trust in the
253 veterinarian, who plays the role of preventive health adviser. These two stakeholders play an
254 important role in responding to public health issues. The relationship between veterinarians and
255 farmers has not fundamentally changed, although some stakeholders in the pig industry believe
256 that their bond has been strengthened. This observation is even truer in farms where the
257 objective was already to reduce the use of antimicrobials before the plan was implemented. In
258 the pig sector, farmers did not question the role of the veterinarian because he was generally
259 perceived as being at the initiative of stopping supplementation.

260 When it comes to antimicrobial usage, farmers can be divided into two categories: those willing
261 to change their antimicrobial usage habits, and those more reluctant to do so (often farmers at
262 the end of their career). Initially, the veterinarians accompanied farmers within the first
263 category. Then, the snowball effect involved most farmers in the dynamic towards reduced
264 antimicrobial usage. The last remaining in the second category are usually those with poor
265 technical management of their post-weaning room. To foster the reduction in the use of
266 antimicrobials, veterinarians adopt several strategies: they reassure farmers by providing
267 guarantees, or they refuse to sign prescriptions for the most reluctant, for example. A small pool
268 of farmers has reportedly maintained their practices, in which case some veterinarians may
269 choose to refuse to sign prescriptions.

270 For feed manufacturers, the development of medicated feed leads to a stock break in
271 manufacturing, as well as a risk of pollution of the production plants. It is therefore not desirable
272 on their part to produce medicated feed; it is a service provided to farmers. The relationship
273 between veterinarians and feed mill technicians seems to be the most negatively impacted by
274 the plan and, more broadly, by the decline in the use of antimicrobials. However, the turnover
275 and the pedagogy made it possible to accompany the changes in a gentle manner.

276 The arrival of antimicrobial-free product labelling has accelerated the decline in use, in
277 particular thanks to Cooperl and Fleury Michon. Even if a hesitation period was observed at the
278 start due to poorly applied and costly solutions, products with a "pigs without antimicrobials"
279 labelling finally served as buffer in the face of increasingly demand on the consumers end.
280 Generally, however, the specifications do not impose a definitive discontinuation of
281 antimicrobials, as a farmer retains his freedom to treat animals if their health situation
282 deteriorates.

283

284 **5.3. Economic effects of the plan**

285 Most actors agree that the Ecoantibio 1 plan only had a very moderate economic impact and, at
286 most, transitory. According to those surveyed, the plan did not have a significant impact on the
287 income of farmers. Farmers highlight that other elements, such as building governance, feeding
288 and breeding management are much more impactful. The direct costs as well as the indirect
289 costs, such as the workload of farmers, were only slightly affected, subject to compliance with
290 preventive measures, such as biosecurity or vaccination strategies. “Safe” feeds sold by feed
291 manufacturers may have represented an additional cost. However, these feeds with higher
292 nutritional value limit digestive problems and therefore the associated expenses. Ultimately, the
293 Ecoantibio 1 plan had no significant impact on pig growth. When a reduction in productivity
294 has been observed, the causes are multifactorial. For example, safe feeds may have led to a
295 reduction in the size of piglets when they contain too low a protein level. A cooperative actor
296 reports that during de-medication after 2012, the average daily gain fell from 810 to 801 grams,
297 to return to its initial value today. The fattening loss rate was 3.2%. Some of the farmers who
298 noticed a decline in growth wanted to return to medicated feed, but most preferred to maintain
299 the change in practice. These have mostly seen compensatory growth during the fattening
300 phase.

301 The veterinarians do not declare having encountered any real economic difficulties after the
302 implementation of the plan. While the drop in revenue generated by curative treatments (sale
303 of antimicrobials) is real, it was partly offset by the sale of preventive products (vaccines,
304 alternatives, diagnostics) over the period of the plan. However, some independent
305 veterinarians have seen their profitability erode, in particular due to the fact that preventive
306 drugs are also marketed by farmers’ groups. In addition, some veterinary groups who have
307 seen their income related to antimicrobials decrease have compensated by asking farmers to
308 participate in livestock health assessments. As for the reduction in the prescription of

309 medicated feed, it often did not affect the veterinary activity as it is feed manufacturers who
310 mostly deal with its trade. Faced with this decrease, veterinary structures sold more oral
311 powders intended for dosing pumps. Some practicing veterinarians have stated that the
312 decrease in turnover per farmer is an opportunity to free up more time for other farmers, in
313 order to balance the overall turnover.

314 There was no significant economic impact for medicated feed manufacturers. It should be
315 noted that the number of specialties has dropped. Supplementation with medicated feed is
316 considered as a service provided to farmers, even if medicated feed leads to stock breaks in
317 manufacturing, as well as risks of pollution at the factory level.

318 Although the economic effects for consumers and distributors are beyond our study, it is
319 interesting to note that during the plan, several specifications were drawn up, such as the "pig
320 confidence"- U system and the labels "antimicrobial-free after 42 days" and "without
321 medicated feed".

322

323 **5.4. Success factors of the Ecoantibio 1 plan**

324 In this section, we highlight the relevant facts which seem to have led, according to the
325 declarations of the people surveyed, to the success of the Ecoantibio 1 plan, in its component
326 of quantitative reduction in antimicrobial use, as well as the broad support of the stakeholders.

327 **5.4.1. Direct State investment and coordination role**

328 Two million euros are allocated per year by the Ministry of Agriculture to research projects
329 and actions aimed at research, knowledge transfer and communication (Figure 1). This allows
330 plan's partners to implement tools such as good practice guides, smartphone applications
331 (Porcisante, GVET) and regulations to prohibit the use of certain critical antimicrobials.

332

333 **Figure 1. Budgets allocated to projects financed by the Ministry of Agriculture and Food for the Ecoantibio**
 334 **1 plan (x €1000).**

335

336 Trainings and meetings between stakeholders seem to have played a role in the effectiveness of
 337 the plan. An Ecoantibio module is included in the training intended for veterinarians for the
 338 sanitary control of farms. In order to develop new non-critical antimicrobials, meetings have
 339 been organized by the Syndicate of the Veterinary Medicines Industry (SIMV) to encourage
 340 public-private partnerships. In addition, the annual conferences organized by ANSES helped to
 341 explain the views of the stakeholders present on the topics of antimicrobial resistance, which
 342 has now become central to the work of the veterinary profession. Notwithstanding the ability
 343 of private actors to support the change in the practices of farmers, it clearly appears, in our
 344 study, that the State plays a key coordinating role. This role had already been highlighted by
 345 Ducrot et al., (2019){Ducrot, 2019 #12669}, who had also described the State in its different
 346 roles –regulatory power, incentive power, and coordinating power.

347

348 **5.4.2.Dynamics in place**

349 The Ecoantibio 1 plan was implemented when a dynamic was already largely at work around a
350 sanitary framework: reduction in the use of antimicrobials, awareness, implementation of
351 specific practices by groups of farmers, improving animal welfare and health.

352 The use of alternatives to antimicrobials was already widespread before the plan was
353 implemented. Historical solutions to limit the use of antimicrobials, such as the implementation
354 of biosecurity or the adjustment of the nutritional quality of feeds have been adopted at a
355 moderate pace, for reasons of economic balance between the cost of antimicrobials and the cost
356 of the measures. Since 2011, ahead of the plan, certain veterinary structures have offered
357 farmers a first-line approach without antimicrobials before considering collective treatment.
358 Faced with a gradual increase in the prices of medicinal premixes and more generally of
359 antimicrobials, as well as a drop in the number of specialties available, pharmaceutical
360 companies have developed their vaccine portfolio. For a sustainable change in practices, and an
361 effective reduction in the use of antimicrobials, the Ecoantibio 1 plan has been able to contribute
362 to strengthening the role of veterinarians as health and zootechnical advisers and to encouraging
363 farmers to change their practices.

364 In addition to the Ecoantibio 1 plan, there are other factors that explain its success. Indeed,
365 regulatory efforts from the public sector (ban the use of growth promoters in animal feed in
366 Europe in 2006) and initiatives from private sector (prudent use of third and fourth generation
367 cephalosporins in 2010) were already in place before 2012 (Table 1).

368

369 **Table 1. Private initiatives and public policies governing the use of antimicrobials in France**

Date	Initiative/Policy
1st January 2006	application of the ban on the use of growth promoters in animal feed (European regulations).

Date	Initiative/Policy
24th January 2007	the Riaucourt ruling of the Council of State reframes the practice of veterinary pharmacy, by prohibiting veterinarians employed by groups of farmers from selling antimicrobials. In response to this ruling, most veterinarians left the groups to join SELAS ¹ , in order to continue to provide comprehensive services to farmers who are members of cooperatives.
1st July 2010	the moratorium on the ban on third and fourth generation cephalosporins comes into force for the pig sector.
25 th October 2012	the prescription circuit is modified, making it more complex and contributing to the reduction in the use of medicated feed.
September 2012	the <i>Cooperl</i> 's farmers launched its production of whole males; this then represented 4% of slaughtered carcasses (10% in 2014 and 12% in 2016). However, no studies exist on the effects of castration on the health of pigs.
January 2014	part of the CASDAR ² budget (130 million euros in total) for the new CAP ³ reform is used for projects aimed at reducing the use of antimicrobials in the pig industry. However, this concerns only one or two research projects
13 th October 2014	The Future Law for Agriculture prohibits laboratories from back discounting on antimicrobials; all customers must now pay the same price
June 2014	<i>Cooperl</i> markets “pork without antimicrobials”.
16 th March 2016	the decree on critical antimicrobials comes into effect. Drugs containing one or more critical antimicrobials are then prohibited for preventive use
June 2016	the group of European Medicines Agency experts AMEG ⁴ chooses not to prohibit the use of colistin for food-producing species, in order to avoid increasing pressure on critical antimicrobials (c3g ⁵ , c4g ⁶ , fluoroquinolones). The group of experts has set a European objective of reducing use by 65% over a period of three to four years.

Date	Initiative/Policy
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¹ SELAS: Private practice company by Simplified Action. SELAS veterinarians are former employees of groups of farmers. It was in 2007 that the Riaucourt ruling of the Council of State prohibited these veterinarians from practicing veterinary pharmacy, in the case where the drugs were bought and/or sold by the group and not by the prescribing veterinarian ² CASDAR: Agricultural and Rural Development Special Account ³ CAP: Common Agricultural Policy ⁴ AMEG: Antimicrobial Advice Ad Hoc Expert Group (AMEG) ⁵ Third generation cephalosporin ⁶ Forth generation cephalosporin

370

371 Stakeholders came together when ANSES reported the emergence of resistance to third- and
 372 fourth-generation cephalosporins in human medicine. By creating a surveillance network for
 373 resistant bacteria of animal origin in the 1990s, and setting up the Inaporc panel in the 2010s,
 374 the pig industry and ANSES have been able to regularly observe the progress made. Some
 375 agricultural unions report that the decline in antimicrobial consumption began before the plan,
 376 with a significant shift in the purpose of their use - from 70% curative to 30% preventive in the
 377 years 1990-2000 to 70% preventive to 30% curative in the 2010s.

378 The reduction in the use of antimicrobials is the result of a collective approach, combining
 379 farmers and veterinarians in the field. Nevertheless, two groups of farmers can be distinguished
 380 with regards to antimicrobial usage: those more willing to change their practices and those more
 381 fearful. Overall, the veterinarians supported the former, from which a snowball effect converted
 382 the latter. The consistency of the responses of the people surveyed, who almost unanimously
 383 mentioned this dynamic, echoes the notion of trajectory of change, developed by Fortane et al.
 384 (2015){Fortané, 2015 #12671}. These authors have shown the importance of networks or
 385 economic and technical objectives in shaping trajectories of change. The role of actors who
 386 provide farmers with diversified resources in terms of methods and knowledge also seemed
 387 central to them.

388 Policies related to the plan have also contributed significantly to the decline in the use of
 389 antimicrobials, such as the moratorium on the latest generation cephalosporins (2010), the
 390 modification of the prescription circuit (2012), the Future Law for Agriculture (2014) and the
 391 the decree on critical antimicrobials (2016). The moratorium on latest-generation

392 cephalosporins, for example, led to a reduction in pig exposure of more than 60% between
393 2010 and 2012, while the number of growing pigs treated fell by 73.3% over the same period
394 {ANSES, 2013 #12659}. Other private initiatives, such as the production of whole males or the
395 production of antimicrobial-free pigs by *Cooperl*, have contributed to reducing the use of
396 antimicrobials. For example, *Cooperl* aimed for the share of animals raised without
397 antimicrobials to reach 10% of the cooperative's production in 2015, with a steady increase in
398 the following years {Process alimentaire, 2014 #12684}. Several television stories, such as
399 "Assiette tous risque" broadcast on France 3 in 2014, have also contributed to the decline in
400 use. The plan was then able to benefit from the built momentum and from the awareness of the
401 stakeholders. Despite some reluctance at the announcement of the quantified objectives of the
402 plan, livestock professionals and veterinarians have been helpful and constructive in applying
403 the reduction in the use of antimicrobials. The success of the plan is the responsibility of each
404 stakeholder, thanks to communication and training.

405

406 **5.4.3. Frail or transitory technical and economic effects**

407 The technical effects of the plan remain limited, as they were added to the initiatives taken
408 previously in terms of vaccination strategy, feed, zootechnics, installation of dosing pumps and
409 commercial labelling of products. Between 2012 and 2016, avoided the use of antimicrobials,
410 but was mainly adopted to counterbalance poor farming practices. Several vaccines have been
411 developed on the respiratory and digestive axes and on piglet edema and several specific
412 practices have been drawn up by producer groups. The quantity of medicated feed and the
413 number of specialties fell ahead of the plan. Farming practices were revised and zootechnicians
414 was placed back at the center of risk management.

415 The economic effects of the plan remain weak concerning the income of farmers, veterinarians
416 and manufacturers of medicated feed. It would seem that the insurance role of antimicrobials
417 has been offset by the implementation of a vaccine strategy at an equivalent cost. Our results
418 are consistent with those of Collineau et al. (2017), who highlighted the possibility of reducing
419 the use of antimicrobials by cost-efficiently implementing biosecurity and vaccination practices
420 {Collineau, 2017 #2468}. Similarly, the IFIP indicates that the drop in the use of antimicrobials
421 does not seem to have deteriorated the technical and economic indicators of pig farmers {IFIP,
422 2021 #12675}.

423

424

425 **6. Conclusions**

426 This retrospective evaluation addressed the need for information on the socio-economic,
427 individual and structural effects of the Ecoantibio 1 plan on the French pig sector. It is an
428 original approach because, to date, there has been no socioeconomic evaluation of public
429 policies to reduce the use of antimicrobials in France. The socio-economic impacts of the
430 Ecoantibio 1 plan appear moderate, both in terms of changes in practices, structural
431 transformations and economic effects. The plan is part of a professional dynamic, initiated by
432 other public policies and private initiatives. From a technical point of view, most of the
433 alternatives to antimicrobials existed before the implementation of the plan and were being
434 used. Relations between stakeholders in the pig industry have been little impacted by the plan
435 or have been strengthened, so no overall negative impacts were detected.

436 A limitation of the study was a lack of quantitative data. Therefore, as this assessment was
437 based largely on qualitative interviews with stakeholders in the pork industry, our results must
438 be extrapolated with caution. Even if the collection of qualitative data is not exhaustive, it was

439 based on the players a priori most impacted by the Ecoantibio 1 plan. The specific economic
440 impacts of the Ecoantibio 1 plan remain difficult to estimate, because they are confounded by
441 other initiatives and changes in the pork sector. In order to have relevant and quantifiable
442 indicators for conducting retrospective analyses, the authors recommend including a reflection
443 on the evaluation of their effects when designing public policies to reduce the use of
444 antimicrobials.

445

446 **7. References**

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